

ADVANTAGES OF USING “BLENDED LEARNING” (FLIPPED CLASSROOM)

Normo‘minova Gulhayo Shavkat qizi

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy
Samarkand State Pedagogical Institute

ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the essence and advantages of using the “Blended Learning” in the modern educational process. In this method, students study the lesson materials independently in advance, and during class sessions they focus on practical tasks, discussions, and group work. The article emphasizes that this technology serves to increase student activity, enhance the effectiveness of the lesson process, use an individual approach, effectively use digital technologies, and develop creativity and critical thinking. The conclusion highlights the contribution of this innovative approach to improving the quality of education.

Keywords: Blended Learning, flipped classroom, modern education, interactive education, independent learning, use of technologies, lesson effectiveness, innovative education, creativity, critical thinking.

This article explores the advantages, pedagogical issues, and models of Blended Learning, particularly the Flipped Classroom approach. Blended learning combines online and face-to-face instruction, enabling students to learn independently through various digital tools and resources while still receiving guidance from teachers. The method shifts the focus from teacher-centered to student-centered learning, emphasizing the development of independent study skills and active participation.

Keywords. Blended learning, flipped classroom, higher education, active student, pedagogy, independent learning, digital tools, teacher preparedness, student-centered learning, rotation model.

In the Blended Learning method, various technologies and tools help integrate information into the learning material. The Internet allows each element to be used in its appropriate place. Students can study information either from books or online — at any convenient time and place. Video lectures are considered a passive process, while reading is an active one. In addition to the main text, various articles and reports can be attached. Sometimes, students are required to search for information on their own. If they are unable to find suitable materials, the teacher can upload the necessary information to their website. Texts can be provided in HTML, DOC, AVI, or MP3 formats.

The concept of the Active Student is considered one of the most essential elements of the Blended Learning structure. Currently, in Europe, this term refers to students studying within a blended learning system. In such models, approximately 50% of a student's activity consists of independent work (mastering materials, participating in forums and chats, communicating via e-mail, etc.). In traditional education, students are taught, whereas in blended learning, they are taught how to learn and guided to organize their own independent activities. In traditional education, the focus is on the teacher (teacher-centered), while in blended learning, the student is at the center (student-centered). Here, the student works more, and success depends on their own efforts. The student can even make adjustments and changes to the learning process. [91, M. Sobirova]

Blended Learning is a form of education based on a combination of online learning materials and group-based learning under the guidance of an instructor. In this form of education, students study independently, but at the same time, receive support from both the instructor and their peers. During group sessions, thanks to the application of blended learning, each student demonstrates positive progress in mastering the material while developing communication skills, reviewing learned topics, and preparing for new ones. Blended learning often relies on assignments and is built around key information, while supplementary materials are provided to students through an online platform. As students study independently, they collaborate with other group members by participating in online discussions.

The proportion of time allocated for classroom and online learning can vary. At different stages of education, distance and independent learning are effectively combined. [55, Ko'makova]

Pedagogical Issues in Implementing Blended Learning Models in Higher Pedagogical Education
When the use of blended learning models in higher pedagogical education is considered as a pedagogical issue, several key aspects need to be analyzed. This issue focuses on identifying factors that hinder effective learning and creating the necessary conditions for successfully implementing blended learning models. Below are some pedagogical challenges that may arise during the use of blended learning models in higher pedagogical education:

Educational resources and infrastructure.

For blended learning models to function successfully, sufficient educational resources and technological infrastructure are required. A lack of technological tools and resources may lower the quality of education and cause students to lose interest in the learning process.

Teachers' methodological preparedness.

To effectively implement blended learning models, teachers must possess high levels of both technological and methodological competence. If teachers lack adequate methodological preparation, they may fail to use blended learning effectively, negatively affecting students' learning outcomes.

Consistency and coherence in education.

Maintaining consistency and coherence is crucial when applying blended learning models. If teachers apply different approaches inconsistently, uncertainty may arise in the learning process, harming students' understanding.

Students' preparedness and perception.

Blended learning models can be a new experience for students. If students do not understand the main principles of blended learning or struggle to adapt, this may negatively affect their educational process.

Pedagogical methods and approaches.

The pedagogical methods and approaches must align with blended learning models. If teachers continue using outdated methods, blended learning will not produce effective results.

Assessment of blended learning quality.

Reliable assessment systems are necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of blended learning models. A lack of clear criteria and methods for evaluation can hinder quality improvement in education. By addressing these pedagogical challenges, it is possible to fully benefit from blended learning and make the educational process more effective.

Rotation Model of Blended Learning

The Rotation Model of blended learning consists of four sub-models:

Flipped Classroom Model

Station Rotation Model

Lab Rotation Model

Individual Rotation Model

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